

Predicting Sugar Profiles of Sweetpotato using Near Infrared Spectroscopy

Kampala, Uganda, 20/12/2024

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTB Breeding project, Quality-component (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods project.

To be cited as:

Judith Ssali NANTONGO, Edwin SERUNKUMA, Joseph KITALIKYAWA, Gilbert AGELU, Mukani MOYO, Reuben SSALI (2024). *Predicting Sugar Profiles of Sweetpotato using Near Infrared Spectroscopy*. Kampala, Uganda: RTB Breeding, Scientific Report, 12 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14979099> .

Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the RTB Breeding project, through a sub-grant from the International Potato Center (CIP) to the French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development (CIRAD), Montpellier, France, incorporated in the grant agreement INV-041105 between CIP and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF).

The authors also acknowledge CIP colleagues; Girisom Bwire and James Kawuma who contributed to the different aspects of the project.

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Final validation by

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26/02/2025

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ABSTRACT

Sweetpotato root quality attributes, such as sweet taste, are among the most desirable traits for growers, consumers and distributors. These sweetness profile of the roots could be partly determined by the chemical composition especially the saccharides. In this work, we quantified the major sugars (sucrose, glucose, fructose, maltose) in sweetpotato and explored their predictability by near infrared spectroscopy (NIRS). We also report some correlations of sweet taste with other sensory traits. To predict the sugars, NIRS calibration models were established with partial least square regression. The suitability of the models was selected based on the coefficient of correlation (R^2) and ratio of performance to deviation (RPD). Robust models were developed for predicting fructose ($R^2 = 0.88$). Relatively low predictive ability was detected for models developed for glucose ($R^2 = 0.52$), sucrose ($R^2 = 0.63$), maltose ($R^2 = 0.52$) and the total of the sugars ($R^2 = 0.56$). These results show that NIR can accurately estimate fructose. All the models had an RPD > 1.40 suggesting that they can have some level of application. Model improvements will be required for predicting the glucose, sucrose and maltose.

Key Words: sugars, maltose, high throughput, sweet taste

1 BACKGROUND

Sweetpotato (*Ipomoea batatas* LAM.) is an important and versatile food crop. With more than 133 million tons in annual production, sweetpotato currently ranks as the fifth food crop in developing countries after rice, wheat, maize, and cassava (Mwanga et al. 2011; Truong et al. 2018). Over the past decade, breeders have progressed, enhancing important production-driven traits of sweet potatoes, such as higher yields, larger roots, pest and disease resistance, and improved farm profitability (Mwanga et al. 2011; Mwanga et al. 2003). However, new breeding approaches must consider consumer requirements to enhance variety adoption. Sweetpotato root quality attributes, such as sweet taste, are among the most desirable traits for growers, consumers and distributors (Leksrisompong et al. 2012; Spence 2015). These sweetness profile of the roots could be partly determined by the chemical composition (Aprea et al. 2017). Studies have correlated chemical composition with sweetness, flavor and other sensory attributes suggesting that the former could be used as a proxy for selected sensory attributes (Oliveira Martins et al. 2023).

Sweet molecules belong to vastly different chemical classes, and they elicit different qualities and intensities. Sucrose, maltose, glucose, and fructose comprise the major soluble sugars in sweetpotato, and these could be major determinants of sweetness (Van Den et al. 1986). Maltose is mostly found in cooked compared to raw sweetpotatoes. Additionally, besides carbohydrates, there is a large spectrum of sweet-tasting molecules including proteins, amino acids, peptides and complex proteins, heterocyclic compounds, terpenoids, flavonoids, and steroidal compounds (Chéron et al. 2017). High throughput prediction of the chemical compounds could be useful in predicting the potentially associated sensory attributes such as sweetness of sweetpotatoes.

Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) has been developed as a fast, mostly non-destructive and economical approach for predicting the contents of chemical compounds. And it has been widely used in scientific and industrial laboratory for qualitative and quantitative analysis of natural products, pharmaceuticals, medical samples. In sweetpotato, modelling of different sensory and sugar composition using NIRS has shown high success (Lebot et al. 2011). In this work, we quantified the major sugars (sucrose, glucose, fructose, maltose) in sweetpotato and explored their predictability by near infrared spectroscopy (NIRS). We also explored the correlations of sensory-based sweet taste with some sensory traits. The results will support rapid estimation of trait levels for sweetpotato breeders to select breeding lines with desirable quality properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Spectra data collection

Spectra were collected from freeze dried samples using an XDS (FOSS, USA) with ISIScan software (Infrasoft International, State College, PA, USA) across the wavelength range of 400 to 2500 nm at 2 nm intervals as indicated by Nantongo et al. (2024b). Each genotype had 3 roots, where each root represented a replicate and one NIR spectrum. The spectrum was expressed as $\log(1/R)$.

2.2 Spectral data analysis

Individual prediction models, using partial least squares (PLS) regression, were developed for each trait. The calibrations were performed using external validation models with waves package in R (v4.4.2). The training

and external validation sets had 250 and 50 samples respectively. The suitability of the calibration equation between chemistry and spectral data was identified based on the coefficient of determination (R²), RPD and RMSE in calibration and validation.

2.3 Biochemical data from sweetpotato roots

The sugars were estimated from 2 g cooked, finely ground sample using 85% ethanol in a shaking water bath at 70°C for 1 h. Each genotype was analysed in triplicate. Sub-samples were averaged/processed to get the mean and standard deviation. The standards for each sugar were prepared using standard methods.

The amount of sugar in each sample was estimated as:

$$\text{Amount of each sugar (mg/g)} = \frac{A_{\text{SPL}} \times C_{\text{STD}}}{A_{\text{STD}}} \times \frac{V}{W}$$

A_{STD}

Where: A_{SPL} = area/peak height of each sugar in sample solution

A_{STD} = area/peak height of sugar standard

C_{STD} = concentration of sugar standard (mg/mL)

V = total volume of prepared sample solution (mL)

W = weight of sample (g)

The Pearson correlation coefficients and statistical significance were estimated in R (v4.4.2).

2.4 Sensory evaluation of cooked sweetpotato

The quantitative descriptive analysis protocol for descriptive sensory analysis of sweetpotato has been previously described (Mudege et al. 2021; Nakitto et al. 2022). In summary, between 9 and 12 trained panellists evaluated each cooked sweetpotato genotype and rated various sensory attributes related to color, aroma, flavor, taste and texture of the sweetpotato samples as presented in a published lexicon 29 on 10-point scales from 0 (minimum intensity) to 10 (maximum intensity).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Amount of sugars in cooked sweetpotato roots

The mean amount of sugars detected in the cooked sweetpotato freeze dried roots analysed is indicated in Figure 1. Maltose formed 69% of the total analysed sugars followed by sucrose (26%) and then fructose (2.6%) and glucose (2.4%). Cooking always increases the amount of maltose relative to the other sugars. A comparison of the raw and cooked samples by (Van Den *et al.* 1986), for example showed that the sum of glucose, fructose, and sucrose accounted for 85-96% and 17-54% of the total sugars in the raw and cooked samples, respectively. However, we expect some changes in the sugars during maturity, storage, and other processing activities. Table 1 summarizes the average, minimum, and maximum measured values of sugars determined using HPLC analysis.

Figure 1: Mean amount of sugars detected in cooked freeze-dried ground sweetpotato roots

Table 1: Statistical attributes of the analysed sugars

	n	Average	SD	minimum	maximum
fructose	300	4.30	5.22	0.04	32.28
glucose	300	3.81	4.47	0	30.10
sucrose	300	42.87	14.02	5.97	92.79
maltose	300	112.34	52.37	0	232.54
Total sugars	300	163.32	63.17	20.73	311.06

3.2 Correlations among the sugars

All the correlations among the sugars were positive and significantly (<0.001) different from zero. However, the highest correlation between the individual sugars was detected between fructose and glucose ($r= 0.78$, $p<0.001$; Table 2). Estimation of total sugars can give an indication of maltose content, given the very high correlation ($r= 0.97$, $p<0.001$)

Table 2: Pearson correlation coefficients of the sugars in cooked sweetpotato roots

	fructose	glucose	sucrose	maltose	total sugars
fructose	1				
glucose	0.78	1			
sucrose	0.23	0.25	1		
maltose	0.30	0.28	0.41	1	
Total sugars	0.44	0.42	0.60	0.97	1

3.3 Correlation with sensory traits

In a separate dataset, sweet taste was weakly correlated with total starch ($r = 0.21$). In this same dataset, sweet taste was highly positively correlated with sweetpotato flavor ($r = 0.88$), which could suggest a strong relationship between these two traits, and that the spectrum of sweet-tasting molecules in sweetpotato could be contributing to flavor. Naturally, we know that the sweet-tasting molecules are chemically diverse and include carbohydrates, proteins, amino acids, peptides and complex proteins, heterocyclic compounds, terpenoids, flavonoids, and steroidal compounds from plants (Chéron *et al.* 2017), which could also be associated with flavor. Sweet taste was also strongly associated with cohesiveness ($r = 0.88$), signifying that

it could have a texture component, and aromatic caramel ($r=-0.88$). Aromatic caramel is the product of non-enzymatic browning reactions that involve the dehydration of sugars during heat treatment under specific conditions. These observations suggest that chemical and physicochemical interactions probably affect both the quality and the intensity of sweet taste response.

3.4 NIR predictions

The unprocessed NIR spectra of the samples are shown in Figure 2. As shown, the spectra are quite homogeneous. No outliers were detected. The spectra were characteristic of other sweetpotato germplasm (Ding *et al.* 2015; Lu *et al.* 2006), where each spectrum has five major peak regions in the following wavelengths; CH second overtone bands (1150 – 1300 nm), NH and OH first overtone bands (1400 – 1700 nm), CH first overtone bands (1700 – 1900 nm), NH and OH combination bands (1900 – 2250 nm) and CH combination bands (2250 – 2400 nm).

Figure 2: Spectra of cooked freeze dried sweetpotato roots

3.5 Prediction models

Near infrared spectroscopy accurately predicted some sugars. The R^2 values between predicted and measured sugars ranged from 0.89 for fructose to 0.52 for glucose and maltose in training samples (Table 3). Similarly, the R^2 for test samples ranged from 0.89 for fructose to 0.24 for sucrose (Table 4). The plots between measured and predicted values is shown in Figure 3. The usefulness and accuracy of developed NIRs models is evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and residual prediction deviation (RPD) values. Models with an R^2 of 0.60–0.82 can be used for initial screening and approximate quantitative predictions, those with R^2 values between 0.83 and 0.90 such as the one of fructose in this work can be used for more accurate applications, while models with R^2 value of 0.92–0.96 are suitable for most applications including quality assurance (Williams 1996). Based on RPD values, models are excellent, where $RPD > 2$; fair where $1.4 < RPD < 2$ and un-reliable with $RPD < 1.4$ (Maurel *et al.* 2010). In this case, based on the training set, all models developed for the sweetpotato sugars can have some level of application. However, based on the test set, the models of sucrose, maltose and total sugars are regarded as unreliable. Generally, sugars in different crops are often well predicted using NIR (Liu *et al.* 2006; Nantongo *et al.* 2024a), and therefore further analysis of the chemical dataset will be done to understand the reason for the inconsistent results of this current work.

Table 3: Performance statistics for NIR models using partial least squares regression from reflectance spectra of sweetpotato training samples (n = 250)

Compound	Pretreatment	R ²	RMSEp	RPD
fructose	Standard normal variate (SNV) and first derivative	0.89	1.69	2.93
glucose	Gap segment derivative (window size = 11)	0.52	3.30	1.47
sucrose	Gap segment derivative (window size = 11)	0.63	8.52	1.65
maltose	SNV + Savitzky–Golay filter (SG)	0.52	35.70	1.44
Total sugars	Standard normal variate (SNV)	0.56	41.70	1.50

Table 4: Performance statistics for NIR models using partial least squares regression from reflectance spectra of sweetpotato test samples (n = 50)

Compound	R2	RMSE	RPD
fructose	0.89	2.32	2.77
glucose	0.57	2.98	1.42
sucrose	0.24	13.99	1.02
maltose	0.42	44.57	1.32
Total sugars	0.46	50.67	1.34

Figure 3: The linear relationship between predicted and lab observed values of the sugars in freeze dried sweetpotato roots

4 CONCLUSION

These data provide preliminary evidence and optimism that NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy using the 400–2500 nm wavelength range can fairly be used to predict sweetpotato sugars including maltose that is related to sweetness. Substantial research is, however, still required to validate the extent to which maltose determines sensory perception of sweet taste since results suggest a correlation with some texture attributes.

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